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Innovative Integration of Phase Change Materials and Conceptual Design of Test Cases – New Products for the Building Envelope

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Abstract. The building sector contributes to a great part of energy consumption and has a major impact on climate in Europe. Development of climate-friendly and energy-efficient products is required to reach low and net-zero energy buildings and to facilitate the energy transition. The building envelope is critical in defining the demand for space heating and cooling as well as ensuring thermal comfort and indoor environmental quality through proper ventilation. This paper presents the conceptual test cases integrating phase change materials (PCMs) in the building envelope. PCM absorbs, stores, and releases the heat energy in a controlled manner taking advantage of the temperature difference between night and day. Hence PCM can support the thermal management of the building by minimizing unwanted heat gains and losses while integrated into walls or support the energy efficiency of ventilation while supplying fresh air. Smart ventilated heat harvesting windows and multifunctional sandwich panels are developed within the EU-funded iclimabuilt project. Additionally, commercial air-guided PCM storages are presented as ready-to-install products for decentralized ventilation and heat recovery systems.

1. Introduction

Building envelope is a key element in providing thermal comfort and a healthy indoor environment as well as contributing to energy consumption and its share of carbon dioxide emission. Development of energy-efficient solutions and low-energy consumption buildings will support the EU energy transition and climate goals [1].

Windows and walls are the main components responsible for major heat gains and losses due to their poor thermal insulation properties [2] [3]. A considerable energy loss also happens through conventional

ventilation despite its insufficiency in improving indoor air quality [4]. Therefore, in this paper energy-efficient solutions that support thermal management and ventilation of buildings will be presented.

Within the EU-funded iclimabuilt project, functional and advanced insulating, energy harvesting and storage materials across climate adaptive building envelopes are being developed to reduce energy consumption in this sector. Hence, two test cases: smart ventilated heat harvesting (VHH) windows and multifunctional composite sandwiches (MCS) with enhanced thermal/energy efficiency and acoustic performance and increased eco-sustainability are being presented. In both test cases, phase change materials (PCMs) are being employed aiming at overcoming the limitations of the conventional building components and reducing the demand for space heating and cooling. The design of these test cases or building systems will be based on a modular, pre-fabricated with plug-and-play concept approach and easy assembling, disassembling, and repair. This is to minimize the amount of on-site work and reduce its associated cost, noise, and waste of raw materials while optimizing the quality. Moreover, air-guided PCM storages for decentralized ventilation systems are also presented.

2. Materials, Components, and Test Cases developed within iclimabuilt

2.1. Smart Ventilated Heat Harvesting Window (VHHW)

In this test case, a ventilated window with additional functions supporting ventilation, thermal management of the accommodation, and indoor air quality was designed by integration of

1. Window module assembly
2. Compact storage module (CSM): Aluminum encapsulated panels filled with the desired phase change material (PCM), as shown in Figure 1 (upper-left)
3. 3D printed acoustic absorbers for fan noise reduction as shown in Figure 1 (down-left) and CO₂ filters for health and well-being
4. Omniphobic coating for self-cleaning properties of the glass

In order to host these elements (PCM plates and acoustic/CO₂ absorbers), two boxes are constructed for integration with the window module as follows:

- **UPPER BOX:** PCM-Air HEX (Heat Exchanger) unit

The upper box contains from left to right as shown in Figure 1 (right): fans, space for air distribution, CSM plates filled with PCM, acoustic absorbers, a motor, and electronics. The PCM-Air HEX unit is designed to maximize the storage capacity without decreasing the transparent area of the window.

- **LOWER BOX:** Indoor air filtration unit

In the bottom part of the window module as shown in Figure 2, a box hosting CO₂ filters and acoustic absorbers, and fans for indoor air circulation only is located. The box is designed to be openable for maintenance and regeneration of the filters.

Figure 1. CSM-plate (450 x 300 x 15 mm), proposed sound absorber (left), and vertical section of PCM-Air heat exchanger (right).

Figure 2. Design of indoor air filtration unit with CO₂ absorbers.

2.2. Multifunctional Composite Sandwiches (MCS) with enhanced thermal/energy efficiency and acoustic performance and increased eco-sustainability.

This test case can be used as structural or non-structural lightweight modular panels for wall construction (internal or external) or as external thermal insulation.

An MCS baseline is produced by replacing standard raw materials with those of lower footprint such as recycled or natural fibers and using better thermoplastic resins to increase sustainability.

To improve the performance of the MCS baseline, functional materials are combined including:

- Multifunctional composite sandwich solutions
- Aerogels as lightweight super-insulation materials for facade elements
- CSM panels filled with phase change materials, shown in Figure 1(upper left), to provide improved thermal stability
- Omniphobic coatings for self-cleaning properties

The arrangement of the MCS with these materials is shown in Figure 3. Sustainability is increased through improvement of the production process and the use of fiber with better properties (laminated epoxy resin with basalt fiber and expanded polystyrene (XPS) core) to produce the multifunctional composite sandwich panel, compared to the initial standard solution (epoxy resin laminate with fiberglass and XPScore).

Figure 3. Schematic of MCS test case in combination of multiple materials.

Figure 4. Localization of the PCM plates and production of the MCS.

The PCM plates were integrated to the composite panel as shown in Figure 4. To do that, the surface of the composite panel and the PCM plates were first sanded and cleaned, then a structural glue was applied to guarantee the union between these two elements and weights were placed above the PCM plates in order to guarantee good adhesion. Finally, this surface was coated with a cementitious mortar.

3. Air-guided PCM Storages for Ventilation and Heat Recovery Systems

3.1. PhaseCube

The PhaseCube developed by Rubitherm [5] is a well-insulated expanded polypropylene (EPP) housing containing ten CSM panels and is compatible with all common ventilation systems. This ensures ease of installation. The main area of application is the cooling of outdoor air in summer. This can be used as a stand-alone system with an inlet, outlet, and fan or to support existing systems, as shown in Figure 5. At night, the PCM releases heat and solidifies. It stores the cold from the night. During the day, this cold storage can be used to pre-condition the outside air for the ventilation/air conditioning system. The standard unit has a total capacity of 1200 Wh and can operate with airflows of 50 – 220 m³/h with a pressure drop of 10 Pa at a volume flow rate of 150 m³/h.

Figure 5. Integration of PhaseCube with existing centralized ventilation system.

Figure 6 shows the performance of the PhaseCube measured within one typical summer day using PCM with a melting point of 21°C and airflow of 150 m³/h. The inlet temperature (red) and the outlet

temperature (blue) within one day. In the beginning, cold air is sucked in at night and passed through the storage unit. The CSM plates cool down, the PCM solidifies and gives off its heat. This can be seen from the blue line. The outlet temperature is higher than the inlet temperature because the PCM has released its heat to the air. Around noon, fresh but warm air is sucked in from outside. The air is forced over the CSM plates and the PCM begins to melt. It absorbs heat from the air and cools it down. In the period from 12:00 p.m. to 4:00 p.m., the air is cooled down from over 30°C to approx. 23°C in average. At night the cycle begins again.

Figure 6. The performance of PhaseCube within one day.

3.2. PhaseDrum

PhaseDrum is a novel, energy-efficient heat exchanger with high heat storage capability using PCM in decentralized ventilation and heat recovery systems. A schematic drawing including the PCM component (red), fan and air filters (grey) is shown in Figure 7. It overcomes the limitations of the counterpart ceramic heat exchangers which are based on sensible heat storage. PCMs can store both sensible and latent heat with energy storage densities per volume which can be 5 -14 times greater than sensible heat storage materials such as ceramics [6]. Moreover, PCMs stabilize the temperature at desired values close to human comfort during the phase change prolonging the time of air regulation.

The innovative integration of a PCM creates a system for the ventilation of interior spaces with a significantly improved switchover time of the fans. The PCM storage allows switching times to be extended to up to 30 minutes as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of PhaseDrum.

Figure 8. Experimental results comparing ceramic HEX and PCM HEX (PhaseDrum).

4. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presented the design of test cases implementing PCMs as future products supporting the heating, cooling, and ventilation in buildings. Besides, already developed PCM storages ready for the market and their installation were shown.

The future work will involve:

- Characterization of the two test cases (TCs) developed within iclimabuilt project in various testing labs and facilities at partners' sites
- Performing thermal simulation and CFD analysis of pressure drop in components in collaboration with iclimabuilt partners
- Performance validation and long-term monitoring of the TCs in a real-time environment through a demonstration of full modules in living labs in different climate zones across Europe

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